

Grant agreement no. 312788

ORCID AND DATACITE
INTEROPERABILITY NETWORK

<http://odin-project.eu>

D2.1 KICK OFF PREPARATION, COMMUNICATION PLAN, AND WEBSITE

WP2 – Communication

V4_0

Final

Abstract: Effective communication is a crucial aspect of the ODIN project. The Communication Plan describes ODIN's approach to engaging with and disseminating project outputs to key target audiences via various channels for the two-year duration of the project. Under this Plan, two items have already been completed: holding the first of three major community events (the "kick off" meeting) and launching a project website. This document outlines our communication strategy and provides a summary overview of our activities to date.

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	WP2: Communication		Dissemination level: PU
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1. INTRODUCTION

As described in the project proposal, the goal of the ODIN project is to identify and resolve issues relating to the ‘missing thin layer’ of persistent identifiers needed for a globally connected and interoperable scholarly communication e-infrastructure. The overall aim is to support development and stimulate adoption of interoperable identifiers for researchers, their inputs (cited work, data) and their outputs (publications and data), and to facilitate information flow within and between research communities, leading to greater re-use of data and innovative exploitation of the knowledge created.

ODIN is not a large-scale infrastructural project and will thus not itself deliver software solutions for production deployment. Rather, ODIN will provide a roadmap which focuses on the integration and scalability of the DataCite (<http://www.datacite.org>) and ORCID (<http://orcid.org>) persistent identifier initiatives for tackling ODIN's four main challenges concerning research data: accessibility, discovery, interoperability, and sustainability. Engaging with and communicating project findings to the relevant communities are crucial components of ODIN's strategy. These and other communication-related project activities are managed by the Communication Work Package (WP2).

The rest of this document describes the key audiences and outlines the communication plan, and is based on our understanding of stakeholder information needs, the types of content that will be disseminated, and the communication channels that will be used. We also report on the “kick off” community event and the project website, both of which are project activities that have been completed.

The Communication Plan is the main part of the first deliverable for WP2: ***D2.1 - Kick off preparation, Communication plan and Website.***

2. TARGET AUDIENCES AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

The four principal groups that ODIN communication activities will target are large and diverse communities which are distinct from each other and have different needs and values:

- **Scientific and research communities**, who rely on a trusted e-Infrastructure to conduct e-Science, and in particular have concerns about the discovery and access to data and the correct attribution of their work, be it publications or, increasingly, data.
- **Funding agencies and policy makers**, including the EC, who are responsible for the rollout of e- Infrastructures and - in this particular context - are called to make strategic decisions concerning data-intensive science.
- **e-Infrastructure designers, builders and operators**, including existing data centres and repositories, who are the “feet on the ground” that will be enabling the ODIN ‘missing thin layer’ of interoperable data and contributor identifiers.
- **The scholarly communications community**, including scientific publishers, libraries and commercial providers of value-added services who need identifiers as those promoted by ODIN to evolve their services, whether commercial or non-profit.

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As elaborated in the ODIN project proposal and Description of Work (DoW), each audience will be taken through an iterative process of engagement, elicitation, reflection and dissemination (see **Figure 1**):

- *We listen:* ODIN collects views and opinions, and subsequent feedback on its findings through them.
- *We investigate:* ODIN collaboratively articulates the current gaps in the e-Infrastructure and success factors, drivers and barriers.
- *They listen:* ODIN disseminates its findings through appropriate channels.
- *They reflect:* ODIN's messages are clear and compelling, enabling strategic decisions to be made and calls for actions to be met.
- *They influence:* ODIN identifies multipliers who have the potential to carry ODIN's messages deeper into communities of interest, adopting and enacting the recommendations and roadmap.

Figure 1: ODIN's iterative process of interacting with target communities

3. COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

The starting point is the relationships that project partners have collectively built up through other projects and initiatives. A crucial example is the way ORCID has, in the last three years, built an enormous momentum across all stakeholders, commercial and non-profit, funding agencies and small-to-medium enterprises (SMEs), research institutions and libraries. Similarly, DataCite has built a large community of diverse stakeholders that are actively engaging with each other.

Note: as the engagement programme evolves, the plan will also evolve and be refined.

For a given target audience that ODIN engages with, we need to understand:

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- what their information needs are and who within the project is responsible for fulfilling those needs
- who within the project is responsible for managing the relationship with each community, with each organisation, with each individual
- their preferred channel(s), ranging from a Twitter feed to a white paper
- the formats we need to put the information into (there may be several)
- the timeline for getting that information to them

The iterative interaction process outlined above is based on a proven model successfully used also by some of the ODIN project partners in previous high-profile support actions, including Parse.insight (<http://www.parse-insight.eu>), SOAP (<http://project-soap.eu>) and ODE (<http://ode-project.eu>). The key to those successes has been to develop progressively deeper levels of engagement with each of the stakeholder groups. With each step their information needs become more specific and our response more focused, based on our understanding of that community.

- 1) *Awareness* - they become aware of the project and the issues it is trying to resolve through peer to peer recommendation, through information provided by the media (both conventional reportage and social media, see **Communication channels** below), through presentations at community-specific events, and so on.
- 2) *Interest* - they begin to explore what ODIN is about. This might be a simple step like following a link on our website, a more focused request for information via email, or starting a discussion with a member of the team at an event.
- 3) *Decision* - based on the information they receive, they may attend one of the key events of the project, workshop or conference (see **Conferences and other events** below), provide information through questionnaires or social media or volunteer to participate in project dissemination as a 'multiplier', for example.
- 4) *Action* - they carry out the decision.

In addition to the various events that ODIN itself will organize, participation of ODIN partners in other international and local events will also be key elements in raising awareness and interest.

Much of the community interaction will take place in the context of specific areas of technical work in ODIN and be especially relevant to certain communities and stakeholder organizations. For example, the two main proof-of-principle projects in WP3 (led by BL and CERN) will, of course, be most relevant to the Humanities and Social Sciences (HSS) and High-Energy Physics (HEP) communities. ODIN partners contributing effort in these work packages will participate in communication and dissemination activities.

Planned activities defined in the DoW for each work package include the following:

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WP3 Proofs of concept (BL, CERN, DataCite):

- Promotion of kick off meeting
- Dissemination of preliminary proofs of concept after first year event

WP4 Interoperability (DataCite, ORCID EU, BL, CERN)

- Dissemination of Hackathon results
- Dissemination of guidelines for integration of the ‘thin layer’ into other services

WP5 Strategy (CERN, BL, DataCite, ORCID EU)

- Ensure participation of key commentators in kick off event
- Dissemination of draft roadmap

WP6 Internationalisation (ANDS, arXiv, Dryad)

- Contribution of international (non-European) views to kick off event
- Dissemination of ODIN progress results to international audiences

A key role of ORCID EU (as lead partner for WP2) is to coordinate and support these activities across all of ODIN. By centralizing core communication activities in WP2 and assigning coordination duties to a single partner, we avoid the risk of a key person holding two similar but not identical conversations with members of the project or, worse still, being asked the same question twice or being given different answers to their own question by different members.

Timing of certain dissemination activities will be key to maximizing the value of project outcomes. As examples of the importance of timing, the ODIN roadmap will be needed one year before the first HORIZON 2020 Calls for proposals (CFPs) for policy-makers and funding agencies to be able to benefit from ODIN recommendations. Also, the availability of open APIs specified by ODIN and implemented by DataCite and ORCID should be communicated as early as possible to potential value-adding partners.

The ODIN project will actively participate in the consultation activities and meetings related to the e-Infrastructures area. The objective is to optimise synergies between projects by providing input and receiving feedback from working groups addressing activities of common interest (e.g. from clusters and projects). Projects may offer advice and guidance and receiving information relating to 7th Framework programme implementation, standardisation, policy and regulatory, EU Member States initiatives or relevant international initiative.

4. CONTENT FOR DISSEMINATION

The primary material for dissemination will be:

- Awareness of the project (website, conference reports, press releases, etc.)
- Concrete proofs of interoperability of identifiers for datasets and contributors, in the most diverse of fields: HSS and HEP
- Case studies describing the status of unique author identifiers today in form of briefs, slides, videos but also formal public reports
- Examples of best practices for citing datasets across the scholarly communication value chain within disciplines but also across systems

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- Analysis of drivers and barriers in data citation and author attribution, targeted to the different stakeholder groups
- Analysis of opportunities for data citation through a spread of e-Infrastructures, both in the education system and to researchers in the International Cooperation Partner Countries (ICPC)
- Analysis of the evolution of the scholarly communication value chain at the onset of a growing move to data citation
- End-of-project study summaries and thematic publications tailored to specific stakeholder groups

Where practical, slides for presentations given by members of the ODIN Consortium at international and/or specialized conferences and meetings will also be collected, as will multi-media presentations (e.g. video recordings) where available.

4.1. Public deliverables

Many of the materials listed are encapsulated in ODIN deliverables are destined for public dissemination, and will be published on the ODIN website:

- D1.1 Project Quality Plan & Project Risk Register (due Sept 2012)
- D2.1 Kick off preparation, Communication plan and Website (due Sept 2012)
- D2.2 Kick off report (due Nov 2012)
- D1.2 First interim scientific report (due Feb 2013)
- D3.1 Proof of concept HSS (due Aug 2013)
- D3.2 Proof of concept HEP (due Aug 2013)
- D4.1 Conceptual model of interoperability (due Aug 2013)
- D5.1 Gap analysis and draft roadmap (due Aug 2013)
- D1.3 First Year Report (due Sept 2013)
- D2.3 First year communication report including results from first year event (due Sept 2013)
- D6.1 International validation of D3.1, D3.2, D4.1 and D5.1 (due Sept 2013)
- D1.4 Second interim scientific report (due Feb 2014)
- D1.5 Second Year Report (due Feb 2014)
- D1.6 Final Report (due Sept 2014)
- D2.4 Final communication report including results from final event (due Sept 2014)
- D3.3 Proof of concepts commonality (due Sept 2014)
- D4.2 Workflow for interoperability (due Sept 2014)
- D5.2 Final roadmap and recommendations for the missing thin layer of the e-Infrastructure (due Sept 2014)
- D6.2 International review of final outputs (due Sept 2014)

In addition to these deliverables already defined in the DoW, papers based on the project findings and methodology are likely to be written. True to the engagement in the Open Access area of project participants, all scientific articles on the ODIN results will be made available as Open Access publications (according to the EC Open Access pilot).

The project will plan activities adequately resourced devoted to dissemination for specialised constituencies and the general public, in particular for awareness and educational purposes. The

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project will consider audience-specific messages about the objectives of the project and its societal and economic impact. The tools to be used will include web-based communication, press releases, brochures, booklets, multimedia material, etc. The dissemination content mentioned above will be regularly updated to provide the latest version of the project status and objectives. Electronic and/or paper versions of this material will be made available to the Project Officer beforehand for consultation and upon its final release.

4.2. Branding

Branding is as important as account management, especially in terms of co-branding with partners' identities and consistency of image. Proper acknowledgement of the source funding, including EU flag and FP7 logo, will be done in all dissemination activities.

The ODIN logo, together with EU flag and FP7 logo, will be used to brand all documents and activities concerning the ODIN project. A set of logos will be placed on the internal wiki website (see below) and thus available to partners for use in presentations and all other material used within the context of the project. The logos of the ODIN project partners will also be added to all presentations and the project website to ensure transparency concerning the background of the ODIN project.

The ODIN support action has a potentially enormous target audience and the resources available to WP2 are limited. This creates a challenge which we will respond to by involving the member organizations of ORCID and DataCite which at the time of writing include >300 organizations covering a wide range of scholarly communication stakeholders, both within and outside Europe. Guidelines will therefore be developed for use of ODIN branding by third parties such as ORCID/DataCite members.

4.3. Communication channels

A number of channels will be used to convey information about ODIN to the target audiences. Full analysis of the major opportunities will be performed as soon as possible at the beginning of the project, so that we can identify when we need specific types of activity before discussing opportunities with, for example, journal editors and science writers in the popular media.

The main channels already active or under consideration include:

Standalone project website - the website was launched at <http://odin-project.eu> in time for the kick off meeting in month 2 (see more below). This initial version of the site contains high-level summary information on the ODIN project (mission, workplan summary, partners, events) and contact information. We will evolve the website further as the project progresses into a central, dynamic hub for dissemination. Features to be added include a project blog for posting news items, compilation of links to project reports, slide decks and other public ODIN-related materials hosted on the site or elsewhere (e.g. blogs and scholarly articles), and more.

Social media - given the widespread and growing use of social networking services in research community (especially the Twitter micro-blogging platform), ODIN partners will take advantage of this by sharing project news and outputs via their social networks as

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appropriate. ODIN-related messages or "tweets" posted by partners will be tagged with the keyword or "hashtag" **#odinproject** which will enable Twitter users to search for and identify them. The live ODIN "Twitter stream" will also be displayed on the front page of the project website.

Web feeds - rather than creating a conventional ODIN E-mail list for public announcements, we will instead augment the project website with a machine-readable web feed in standard RSS/Atom formats and advertise this prominently on the front page of the project website and elsewhere. Users can then subscribe using a feed reader service or application of their choice (e.g. Google Reader) to keep up to date with new content on the project website. A link to the site feed will be shown prominently on the front page of the project website and promoted elsewhere.

Mailing lists - ODIN partners are members of a diverse range of regional, discipline, trade or otherwise focused E-mail lists. As with social media strategy, partners will share project news & outputs as appropriate via those lists.

Talks, papers and posters at conferences and workshops - both general events and those aimed at particular key subsets of our target audiences.

The 'business' press will be used to reach scientific and IT professionals (papers, interviews, press releases, press conferences, media packs and short reports) and we shall produce our own act-sheets and case-studies, brochures and targeted reports. We include IT professionals as a target group on account of the plans for collaboration with added-value service providers.

5. CONFERENCES AND OTHER EVENTS

In-person events are a crucial part of ODIN outreach activities. As noted above, participation by partners in relevant conferences in the field are an important part of the overall communication strategy. Much of the communication and dissemination work in WP2 (and across several other work packages, as already noted) will be concentrated around three main events: the initial kick off meeting and conferences near the end of years 1 and 2.

5.1. Initial kick off meeting (M2)

ORCID and DataCite organized an initial "kick off" event which brought together the project partners and several key stakeholders in e-Infrastructures for data interoperability and/or scholarly communication. As described in the project proposal, the aim of the meeting was to get perspectives from the stakeholder community on present gaps and the perception for the missing "thin layer" of interoperable identifiers.

The kick off meeting took place at Kalkscheune, in Central Berlin on October 18th. The date and location were chosen to coincide with the ORCID Outreach meeting (<http://about.orcid.org/civicrm/event/info?reset=1&id=6>) held the previous day at the Grimm-Zentrum library at Humboldt University, also in Central Berlin. Co-locating these two events was key to ensuring kick off participation by several stakeholder representatives who were in town for the ORCID meeting. Several stakeholders had been contacted individually through existing ODIN partner contacts and asked to participate, including both local organizations (e.g. the GESIS Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences, a major research data infrastructure provider in Germany) and organizations from outside of Europe (e.g. SSRN - Social Science Research

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Network). This promotional strategy produced a group of around 30 kick off participants, divided roughly equally between ODIN partners and non-partners, a size and composition that proved ideal for fostering discussions and exchanging ideas.

Annex A contains the kick off meeting programme and list of all participants. Slide decks from all presenters have been posted on the ODIN website (<http://odin-project.eu/events/kick-off/>). A report from the meeting is currently being prepared (*D2.2 Kickoff report*).

5.2. 1st year conference and hackathon (M11)

The first of the two major ODIN community events will be held at CERN near the end of the first year. This will be a combination of a traditional-style conference and a technology-focused, hands-on hackathon. The conference part will enable the ODIN group to disseminate findings and to obtain feedback & validation on the work completed so far. The hackathon part will be a venue for participants and invited experts to work together to assemble concrete demonstrations of the potential of open and interoperable identifier systems.

5.3. Final 2nd year conference (M23)

The other major ODIN community event will be hosted by BL near the end of the second year. The final conference will consolidate delegates' understanding of the project's findings, and develop recommendations for all stakeholders to implement the ODIN roadmap pertinent to their sphere of activity.

In addition to the above major events, ODIN will also be on the lookout for opportunities to co-organize smaller events or workshops, such as half day - 1 day workshops co-located with (or as sessions within) other events, such as the DataCite and ORCID meetings (held 1-2 times each year) and scientific conferences.

All three main ODIN events are listed in the Events section on the project website (<http://odin-project.eu/events/>). Event dates, other event details and materials will be posted as they become available. Other ODIN-affiliated events will also be listed on this page.

6. INTERNAL COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

As with any collaborative undertaking of this scale, effective intra-project communication is vital to success. ODIN will rely several measures to keep partners up to date with developments, share materials and exchange ideas:

Mailing list - CERN manages a closed E-mail list for the ODIN project (odin-fp7-project@cern.ch). At least one person from each partner organization is a member of this list. All members can post freely to the list which facilitates unrestricted, unmoderated discussions amongst project partners.

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Internal wiki -CERN also hosts the closed project wiki (<https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/viewauth/ODIN/>) to which at least one person from each partner organization has access.

Bi-weekly conference calls - Partners have agreed to meet via teleconferences every other week for routine reporting on progress within each work package and to discuss any other issues. Minutes are taken from conference calls and posted to the project wiki and disseminated via the mailing list.

As ODIN partners are spread widely across timezones, finding a conference time that is convenient for everyone proved impossible. The current plan is therefore for non-Europe partners (Dryad, ANDS, arXiv) to join every other conference (i.e. once per month), to minimize the inevitable disruption from teleconferences at odd hours (typically 6am or 12pm) for those partners.

Bi-annual in person project meetings - Face to face interactions are a key element in a successful collaboration, and so ODIN partners will gather for intra-project meetings twice each year. For convenience and cost-saving purposes, we will attempt to schedule project meetings with major events in this space that many partners will also be attending (including, naturally, the 1st and 2nd year ODIN conferences).

The first project meeting took place Oct 19th 2012 immediately following the kick off meeting in Berlin. The second meeting will be held in late spring 2013 and co-located with a suitable event (e.g. the next ORCID Outreach meeting in Oxford, UK in May 2013).

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ANNEX A – KICK OFF MEETING PROGRAMME AND PARTICIPANTS

Programme

08:30-09:00 Registration

9:00 - 10:30 Introduction/Vision

Welcome, Salvatore Mele (CERN)

The DIGOIDUNA study: main conclusions and moving forward, Paolo Bouquet (OKKAM)

The ODIN vision: introduction to the project, Jan Brase (DataCite)

Lessons learned by CrossRef, Ed Pentz (CrossRef)

10:30 - 11:00 Coffee Break

11:00 - 12:30 Challenges/Barriers, Moderation: Salvatore Mele (CERN)

Input from funders, Verena Weigert (JISC)

Input from data centers, Brigitte Hausstein (GESIS)

Input from citation databases, Michael Habib (Scopus/Elsevier)

12:30 - 13:30 Lunch Break

13:30 - 15:00 Opportunities: Improve Interoperability, Moderation: Laure Haak (ORCID EU)

Input from ISNI/VIAF (Janifer Gatenby)

Input from institutional repositories, Pablo de Castro (GrandIR)

Input from libraries, Lambert Heller (TiB Hannover)

15:00 - 15:30 Coffee Break

15:30 - 16:30 Opportunities: We are not Alone, Moderation: Jude England (British Library)

Input from Japan, Hideaki Takeda (National Institute of Informatics, Japan)

Input from US, Gregg Gordon (SSRN)

16:30 - 17:00 Wrap-up, Conclusions, "Take home message" for ODIN, Moderation: Jan Brase (DataCite)

List of participants

Name	Organization	City	Country/region
Mr. BIJSTERBOSCH, Magchiel	SURF	Utrecht	NETHERLANDS
Mr. BOUQUET, Paolo	OKKAM	Trento	ITALY

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Mr. BRASE, Jan	DataCite	Hannover	GERMANY
Mr. BROWN, Josh	JISC	London	UK
Mr. BURTON, Adrian	ANDS	Canberra	AUSTRALIA
Mr. CASTRO, Pablo de	GrandIR	Madrid	SPAIN
Mrs. DAGIENE, Eleonora	The Association of Lithuanian Serials	Vilnius	LITHUANIA
Ms. DALLMEIER-TIESSEN, Suenje	CERN	Geneva	SWITZERLAND
Mrs. ENGLAND, Jude	British Library	London	UK
Mr. FENNER, Martin	ORCID EU	Hannover	GERMANY
Mrs. GARCIA GÓMEZ, Consol	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - BarcelonaTech	Castelldefels	SPAIN
Mrs. GATENBY, Janifer	OCLC	Leiden	NETHERLANDS
Mr. GORDON, Gregg	SSRN	Rochester	USA
Mrs. HAAK, Laure	ORCID EU	Bethesda	USA
Mr. HABIB, Michael	Elsevier	Amsterdam	NETHERLANDS
HAUSSTEIN, Brigitte	GESIS Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences	Berlin	GERMANY
Mr. HELLER, Lambert	TiB Hannover	Hannover	GERMANY
HILL, Amanda	Names Project/University of Manchester	Consecon	CANADA
Mr. KAYE, John	British Library	London	UK
Mr. KRAMER, Stefan	Open Data Foundation	Berlin	GERMANY
Mr. MELE, Salvatore	CERN	Geneva	SWITZERLAND
Ms. PAGLIONE, Laura	ORCID	Bethesda, MD	USA
Mr. PENTZ, Ed	CrossRef	Oxford	UK
Mr. ROUS, Bernard	Association for Computing Machinery (ACM)	New York	USA
Ms. RUEDA, Laura	CERN	Geneva	SWITZERLAND
Mr. SHILLUM, Chris	ORCID/Elsevier	New York, NY	USA
Mr. TAKEDA, Hideaki	National Institute of Informatics	Tokyo	JAPAN
Dr. THORISSON, Gudmundur	ORCID EU	Reykjavik	ICELAND
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